

A STUDY ON THE TELEVISION VIEWING HABITS OF GENERATION Z WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO BANGALORE CITY

S.Hemanthkumar¹

¹Assistant Professor, M P Birla Institute of Management, Bangalore, Karnataka, India,

Mohit Kallur²

²Student, MBA 2014-2016, M P Birla Institute of Management, Bangalore, Karnataka, India,

ABSTRACT

The Indian Media and Entertainment (M&E) industry is a sunrise sector for the economy and is making high growth strides. Television has become one of the most important mass media tools especially in recent years. Dorr(1986) states that TV stands out from other media as it is generally used more and can present more lifelike content than most of other media. Television habits consist of patterns of behavior determined by the amount of time and importance individuals give to watching television broadcasts and recorded videos and DVDs. It is generally believed that television has become a very powerful medium and its contact, no doubt, can change the likes and dislikes, learning and social habits. The impact on the personality and the television viewing has a significance difference with reference to genres so it has been suggested that to improve the content of the programs which helps the viewer to enhance their knowledge. The viewing habits of the generation Z television viewers are likely to switch towards the internet streaming medium to get rid of commercials and their viewing time is mostly by the evening slot so its suggested to have productive shows and programs.

KEYWORDS : Generation Z, Habits, Media, Television, Viewers

I .INTRODUCTION

A Television, commonly referred to as TV or Television is a telecommunication medium used for transmitting sound with moving images in monochrome (black-and-white), color, or in three dimensions. It can refer to a television set, a television program, or the medium of television transmission. Television is a mass medium, for entertainment, advertising and news.

History of Indian Television Industry:-

History of Indian Television lays bare the journey of television and the assorted highs and lows. The prestigious history of Indian television has envisioned the progress, expansion and growth of audio visual media in the nation. Television in India has been in existence for about four decades. The rapid expansion of television hardware in India increased the demand for developing

more program software to fill the broadcast hours. Program production, previously a monopoly of Doordarshan, the government-run national television system in India, was then opened to the group of aspiring artists, producers, directors, and technicians.

Television and its Influence:-

Television has been, without doubt, a godsend to the modern society, since it has served as a common communications receiver in numerous homes, businesses and institutions. In my opinion, television, as a main source of knowledge, entertainment and news, has been increasingly conducive to the sharing and exchange of ideas, and raising social awareness. television benefits the communication by providing entertainment and up-to-day news and events, many argue that it has caused many unexpected consequences. By way of example, many television programs have misled children by offering

messages about violence, sexual alluring and blood contents. Nevertheless, those problems could be avoided if parents are restricting their children to watch some particular TV programs that are watched by their children.

II. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the present study is to examine the watching habits of different TV programs among students and youth. Apart from this, other objectives of the study are as follows;

1. To study the genre impact on personality and television viewing habits.
2. To analyze significance differences for various channels watched and commercials which appear in that channel.
3. To gain an insight into the categories of programs preferred by respondents.
4. To examine whether commercials act as distractions or medium of information for respondents.
5. To study the relationship between frequencies with which television is watched with brand recall.

IV. DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1: Showing Testing of Hypothesis to Analyze Significant Relationship between watching Television.

HYPOTHESIS	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	F-Value	P-Value	ACCEPTED/REJECTED
Action/Thriller genre impact on your personality and television viewing has significant difference to each other.	5%	9.241	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis is accepted
Documentary/Factual Genre impact on your personality and television viewing has significant difference to each other.	5%	6.692	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis is accepted
Music genre impact on your personality and television viewing has significant difference to each other.	5%	1.730	0.15	Null Hypothesis is accepted
Sports Channels you watch and the commercials which they appear in that channel has significance difference of each other.	5%	6.492	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis is accepted
Kids Channels you watch and the commercials which they appear in that channel has significance difference of each other.	5%	0.781	0.510	Null Hypothesis is accepted
There exists relationship between frequencies with which television is watched with brand recall	5%	92.574	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis is accepted
Lifestyle Channels you watch and the commercials which they appear in that channel have significance difference of each other.	5%	22.192	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis is accepted
Commercials do act as distractions but act as information medium for respondents.	5%	70.903	0.000	Alternative Hypothesis is accepted
Personality and types of channels are Significant different of each other.	5%	9.241	0.001	Alternative Hypothesis is accepted

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data Collection:-

- ☐ Primary data has been collected using a structured and focused questionnaire; which covered various dimensions of the research questions. Convenient sampling technique was used to collect data for the research. The sample size consisted of 100 Television viewers which involved generation Z viewing habits between the age group of 15 -25.
- ☐ Secondary data has been collected from books, internet, literature and other relevant documents. Magazines, Journals, Fact sheets and Web resources, online libraries and websites are other sources.

Statistical Techniques Used:-

Chi square test:-

The application of chi square test in this study was to find out whether their exist significant relationship between watching television during the time when commercials are played. The test was also used to find out whether their exist significant relationship between watching television frequently and brand recall.

ANOVA:-

ANOVA was applied to analyze significance differences for various channels watched and commercials which appear in that channel. Similarly it intended to gain an insight into the categories of programs preferred by respondents.

V. FINDINGS

Television viewing habits of Generation Z with special reference to Bangalore city mainly studies about the viewing habits of 15-25 years old age group viewers. The below are the findings we found after the survey conducted.

- ↻ A genre which impact on the personality and television viewing has a significant difference to each other all the genres has significant difference with each other except the music genre.
- ↻ Most of the respondents watch programs in a traditional television itself where there is switching towards internet streaming way of watching programs.
- ↻ Majority of the respondents has said that commercials are very big distractions and also the impact of time limit of the commercials most of respondents likely to have 20-40 sec maximum limit for commercials.
- ↻ Respondents do agree that television viewing helps them in their career, buying og the branded products and recalling the particular brands.
- ↻ Commercials on the favorite channels where most of the respondents are in neutral stage where commercials which gives information about product or not, some of the respondents do watch when they appear and most of them swap to other channels.

VI .SUGGESTIONS

As the commercials are been said as destructions as per the survey results advertisers are been advised to post their ads in other medium like social media, print media etc., and get reduced the cost of their production as well as it helps to the final consumer too. It also suggested that as per that survey conducted most of the respondents would watch television in the timing between evenings, so it would be good to give programs like personality developments, information about the career etc., As the most of the respondents are agreed that they recall brands with significance difference between the recalling of brands and frequently watching of television .The impact on the personality and the television viewing has a significance difference with reference to genres so it has been suggested that to improve the content of the programs which helps the viewer to enhance their knowledge.

VII. CONCLUSION

Television viewing habits of generation Z has impact on many things this project only with reference tothe television viewing, buying behavior, personality development and also viewing habits which help to make ones career prospects and so on, the genres has direct link to the career aspects as per the survey and also people do not like the long time commercials which will appear while watching the television programs it's not about the individual company advertisements but as a whole respondents are very much distracted when the lengthy advertisements broadcasts in between. As the respondents are more like to switch towards the internet streaming sources to watch their favorite programs without any commercials in it, the authorities should take care of the timings of the commercials. The overall conclusion is the viewing habits of the generation Z television viewers are likely to switch towards the internet streaming medium to get rid of commercials and their viewing time is mostly by the evening slot so its suggested to have productive shows and programs.

REFERENCES

1. Valaskakis, Gail (1983), *Television Viewing Tastes and Habits among the Inuit of the Eastern And Central Arctic,* " *Anthropologica* 25(1), 71-83.
2. Dorr Aimme (1986). *Television And Children:A Special Medium For Special Audience*, Sage, Thousand Oaks.
3. Lowery, Shearon and Melvin L. DeFleur (1988) *Milestones in Mass Communication Research*. New York, NY: Longman Inc.
4. Shmizu, S. (1993). *The Implication Of Trans-Border Television For Natural Cultures And National Broadcasting: A Japanese Perspective*. *Media Asia*. Singapore: *An Asian Mass Communication Quarterly*, 20,183-197.
5. Unnikrishnan N and Bajpai (1996). *Impact Of Television Advertising On Children*, 4th Edition, Sage, New Delhi.
6. Fatima, Nabiha (2000). *Effects of Satellite Channels (ZEE TV) on Middle Class of Lahore*. M.A. Thesis, University of the Punjab, Lahore, 60 .
7. Bukhari, Bushra (2002). *The Effect of Television Programmes on Youth*. M.A. Thesis, University of the Punjab, Lahore, 67.
8. Giacomo Corneo, (2002). *Work and Television*, CESifo Working Paper Series No. 829; IZA Discussion Paper No. 376 .
9. Ahluwalia, A.K and Singh, R. (2011), *TV Viewing Habits Amongst Urban Children*, *IUP Journal Of Marketing Management*, Vol. 10(1),45-62